

ISic1504

I.Sicily inscription 1504

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Found by Orsi in 1928 in contr. Diana, reused as cover of t.14

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 2386

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334826

1. Κύϊντος
2. Βαλέριος Νί-
3. γερ Ἄρτεμι-
4. σίου υ-
5. ιός.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645005

PHI 334826

Bibliography

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 718
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